
Higher Education System in India: Problems, Challenges & Suggestions

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DOI - 10.5281/zenodo.15559559

Introduction:

Higher education means different things to different people. If we talk about higher education in terms of level, it means to gain higher educational qualification by the teaching-learning process in the higher educational institutes such as colleges and universities. Moreover higher education imparts knowledge, develops the student's ability and also give him/her a wider perspective of the world around. Higher education becomes input to the growth and development of industry and also seen as an opportunity to participate in the development process of the individual through a flexible education mode.

Higher Education in India Level:

Next to China and United States India has the third largest higher education system in the world in terms of size and its diversity and largest in the world in terms of number of educational institutions. After independence Indian higher education attain a massive growth In the Indian system, higher (tertiary) education starts after the Framework of higher education in India is very complex. It includes various type of institutions like universities, colleges, institutes of national importance, polytechnics etc. Universities are also of different types like central universities

which are formed by government of India, by an act of parliament which are responsible for arranging and distributing resources required by university grant commission (UGC), State universities, Deemed universities (aided and unaided) and Private universities. India has a federal set-up and the Indian constitution places education as a concurrent responsibility of both the centre and state. While the centre co-ordinates and fixed standards in higher and technical education, school education is the responsibility of state under the department of higher education there are several regulatory bodies and research councils which are responsible for the higher education in India.

Female Faculty in Higher Education:

A study pratibha Jolly, Priyanka Nupur and Roja Rawat “ Women in Higher Education “ Deccan Herald sept, 13-2021. P.6 has found that the number of females faculty in postgraduates and research departments is very low. According to NIRF (National institutional Ranking frame work) While female enrollments and out- turn in higher education is on the ascendant there is lack of equitable career opportunities in higher academia. The number of female faculty in postgraduate and research departments is abysmally low. It is found

that NTRF top university have just 10% female Vice -chancellors. The engineering institutions have merely 7% women directors. The prestigious IITs and IISERs have never had a women director. The NIRF gender leadership index is a wakeup call. The study has observed that as the new education policy reboots the system there is need to change mindsets, improve organizational culture, gender climates and lived experience of the community women in decision making roles can catalyze new ways of thinking and doing

Main Features of Indian Higher Education System:

- Highly bureaucratized system with multiple controls and regulations exercised by Central and State Governments, statutory bodies (University Grants Commission (UGC), All India Council of Technical Education (AICTE) and others), university administration and local management.
- System is heavily subsidized by the Government. Up to 90per cent of the operating costs are paid for by the state. The efficiency of fund utilization is very poor due to internal rigidities.
- Salary and compensation for teaching staff is poor and, therefore, higher education institutions are unable to attract and retain qualified and trained teachers. Besides unattractive compensation packages, recruitment procedure is lengthy and working environment not conducive to retention. As a result, a substantial proportion of high ranking students who could fill up such assignments prefer to work

elsewhere or go abroad. In a recent move UGC has further damaged the pay and promotion prospects of college teachers by reducing promotional grades thereby creating more stagnation and frustration amongst college teachers.

- Most institutions offer outdated programmes with inflexible structures and content. While course content has been updated and restructured over time in the world's best institutions, Indian university curricula have lagged behind.
- Infrastructural facilities range from inadequate to dismal. Classrooms are often unattractive and laboratories inadequately stocked, leading to poor teaching. It is estimated that barely 20per cent of the institutions have the basic minimum laboratory equipment.
- Steady electric power supply is not available. Laboratories are poorly stocked and computerization, where it exists is generally dependent on poor communication lines (Kaul, 2006).

A sound higher education sector plays an important role in economic growth and development of a nation. Higher education, in terms of its relevance and importance, enjoys a significant position in the education system as it equips people with appropriate knowledge and skills to be gainfully employed. India has one of the largest systems of higher education in the world offering facility of education and training in almost all aspects of human creativity and intellectual endeavour. In the context of current demographic structure of India where the majority of population is below the age of 25 years, the role of higher education is critical.

Challenges In Tqm Implementation In Higher Educational Institutions:

Leadership: Unlike CEO's of business organizations, Vice Chancellors/Directors of Universities/Institutions do not enjoy ultimate authority hiring and firing personnel and allocating resources. Institutional heads can set goals, organizational values and performance expectations. However since they lack necessary authority, it is difficult for them to deploy these values and goals through the layers of higher education institutions.

Cultural and Organizational transformation: Many business organizations have adopted TQM and transformed their institution's culture into a total quality culture that involves elements such as teamwork, employee participation, customer and market focus etc. However higher education institutions have deep-rooted traditions dating back to several centuries and are resistance to change. Eg. Universities and colleges are organized on departmental units. In adopting TQM culture, organizations move from product focus to market focus. But for faculty, particularly research faculty, primary loyalty lies in the academic field. Market requirement for their students are of secondary importance to them except for some professional schools as business and engineering. In business organizations there is cross linkage and well communication between the various functional departments. But in the case of higher educational institutions, most of the individual departments operate in vacuum. This is one reason that interdisciplinary study and research is a rarity.

Customer Identification: A different aspect of customer issue here is customer loyalty. In

businesses, customer loyalty is very important because repeat buying by loyal customers' has a direct effect on profitability. However higher education is "once in a lifetime activity". If students are considered as customers, this concept makes sense only when they make donations as alumni. However if employers are customers, repeat purchase means recruiting at same institutions every year.

Some Measures Scheme for improving Higher Education in India:

The role of higher education in the growth and progress of a nation has been well recognized for centuries. There are many areas where we need reform higher education. Our main aim must be to nurture excellence instead of spending a disproportionate amount of energy trying to curb the lack of it. It is the responsibility of the UGC to maintain the quality of our higher education and research. The country needs skilled and trained faculty and researchers for making India superpower in the world. For this, there are some possible measures for improving quality in higher education:

1. In India, the first step towards improvement should be taken at school level with aptitude tests being introduced to know where the interest of the student lies. These students should then be encouraged to join those fields of interest.
2. India is a promising investment market and itself has to step up its efforts to create investor confidence and build an enabling investment climate.

3. Indian government should take steps to give more students access to a college education. The goal now is to more than one and half the number of 18 - 23 year olds who enroll in higher education, from the current estimated 20 percent to 30 percent. According to the HRD Ministry, to achieve this goal, India will need to add more than 45,000 new universities and colleges in the coming decade.
4. E-Learning appears to be a fast emerging mode of global entry at the present time. The Universities and other Institutions of higher education can design their web sites for offering online education worldwide.
5. Indian institutions and regulators should restore transparency, coherence and confidence in the higher education system both at home and abroad.
6. Laboratories should be updated and obsolescence in equipment/facilities should be removed on a regular basis. Innovative practices related to examination reforms should be empirically tested and institutionalized. All the examination processes should be computerized and recent advances in ICT should be exploited to make the process automated and efficient.
7. Emphasis should be laid on not just increasing the number of higher education institutes but Centre of excellence. Great stress must be laid on good infrastructure and facilities. Achievers in every field should be rewarded adequately.
8. Libraries should be fully equipped with the latest books, journals and periodicals. A library must be online and conducive for serious study. Make available high quality e-text books, e-reference books, e- research papers and e-content in different languages free of cost to genuine learners.
9. Most of the areas identified for export of higher education are directly concerned with industries. Therefore, Central and State Governments should introduce a range of programmes and incentives designed specially to improve the links between Universities and Industry. The Universities and National Institutes of higher Learning should design their courses in collaboration with industry and such courses be updated regularly, e.g., every year, according to need.
10. Multi-disciplinary mission mode research and innovation programmes should be evolved in association with arts, humanities and social sciences which should directly benefit the society. In order to achieve this, every University should allocate a certain proportion of their annual budget as an earmarked budget for research and innovation.
11. Public Private Partnership (PPP) is most essential to bring in quality in the higher education system.

Conclusion:

In this paper we have presented the present situation of India in higher education sector. We also identify the challenges like

demand-supply gap, lack of quality research, problem of infrastructure and basic facilities, shortage of faculty etc in the higher education. The implementation framework for twelfth plan aims to focus on improving quality of state institutions, to revamp financial aid programs, to interlink expansion, equity and excellence. To improve the higher education system we need to improve teaching pedagogy, build synergies between research and teaching, facilitate alliance of higher institutions among themselves, research centers and industries. This is necessary not only to take care of economic growth, but it is also essential for social cohesion and to empower the country's youth.

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